

Linnæus University

Monthly Report October 2025

SENTINEL Wild Birds

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SUMMARY REPORT

1. OVERVIEW

SENTINEL Wild Birds aims to enhance the understanding of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus dynamics in wild bird populations by conducting active surveillance at key locations in and near Europe. These locations are divided into the following surveillance nodes: Node 1 Gulf of Finland (Finland, Estonia), Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland), Node 4 Eastern Black Sea (Georgia), Node 6 Lake Constance (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), Node 7 Veneto Region (Italy), Node 8 Camargue (France), and Node 9 Gulf of Cadiz (Spain). This monthly summary provides an update on sampled wild birds as part of an early warning system to support wildlife management and disease prevention efforts. The data in this report are based on previously unpublished samples collected from June 2025 to October 2025.

2. RESULTS

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

Since the last monthly report was published on 7th of October 2025 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17287099>), and as of 15th October 2025, test results have been submitted for 3,335 samples taken from 1,966 individuals representing 55 taxa from six nodes in Europe (Table 1). Of the 3,335 collected samples, 1,505 (45%) were cloacal swabs, 1,376 (41%) tracheal/oropharyngeal swabs, 365 (11%) fecal samples, 70 (2%) combined swabs (choana + cloacal), 15 (<1%) pooled organs, and 4 (<1%) feather samples. Of all samples, 386 (12%) were positive for avian influenza virus, with one sample (a Mallard from Latvia) positive for highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus (Figure 1; Table 2). In addition to this HPAI virus-positive sample, virological analysis (by PCR) confirmed one H13N6 virus in a European Herring Gull from Lithuania, one H6N5 in a Mallard from Austria, as well as one H3N2, one H6N5, one H12N2, and two H5 viruses with undetermined NA subtypes, all in hunted Mallards from Latvia.

The most sampled species were Mallard (612 individuals), Eurasian Teal (429 individuals), Dunlin (167 individuals), Sandwich Tern (121 individuals), and Common Tern (97 individuals; Table 1). High bird-level prevalence in species with a sample size of at least 50 individuals was found in Eurasian Teal (19%), Mallard (13%), and Black-headed Gull (11%; Table 1).

TABLE 1 Most recently sampled individuals in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of individuals sampled in the wild, number of individuals tested positive for avian influenza virus as well as bird-level prevalence. The table includes previously unpublished samples from June October 2025.

Group/species	Node 1	Node 2	Node 2	Node 2	Node 4	Node 6	Node 6	Node 6	Node 7	Node 9	Total												
	Finland	Latvia	Lithuania	Sweden	Georgia	Austria	Germany	Switzerland	Italy	Spain	Ind.	Pos.	Prev.										
<i>Waterfowl</i>																							
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	16	0	0	0	0	19	1	5%							
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	5	0	0%							
Barnacle Goose	50	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	51	0	0%							
Mallard	36	8	28	5	0	0	442	48	100	16	4	1	0	0	0	612	78	13%					
Domestic Mallard	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	3	10%					
Gadwall	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0%					
Northern Pintail	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0%					
Northern Shoveler	2	0	7	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	11	4	36%					
Eurasian Wigeon	0	0	6	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0%					
Eurasian Teal	1	1	0	0	0	0	7	3	420	76	0	0	0	0	0	429	80	19%					
Garganey	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	2	25%					
Common Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	4	44%					
Red-crested Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%					
Tufted Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	100%					
Goldeneye	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%					
Common Merganser	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%					
<i>Grebes</i>																							
Great Crested Grebe	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%					
Little Grebe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0%					
<i>Cormorants</i>																							
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	32	0	0	0	6	0	0	38	0	0%					
<i>Hérons</i>																							
Black-crowned Night Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0%					
Western Cattle Egret	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	4	0	0%					
Little Egret	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0%					
<i>Storks, Ibises et al.</i>																							
White Stork	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0%					
Glossy Ibis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0%					
<i>Rails</i>																							
Common Moorhen	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	0%					
Eurasian Coot	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30	0	0%					
<i>Waders</i>																							
Black-winged Stilt	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0%					
Charadrius sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%					
Little Ringed Plover	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	23	0	0%					
Common Ringed Plover	12	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	21	0	0%					
Grey Plover	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%					
European Golden Plover	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%					
Ruff	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0%					
Red Knot	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%					
Purple Sandpiper	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%					
Dunlin	56	0	0	0	109	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	167	0	0%					
Curlew Sandpiper	1	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	7	0	0%					
Temminck's Stint	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0%					
Wood Sandpiper	14	0	0	0	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	46	0	0%					
Green Sandpiper	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	6	0	0%					
Common Sandpiper	2	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0%					
Common Redshank	6	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0%					
Spotted Redshank	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%					
Common Snipe	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0%					
<i>Larids</i>																							
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	0	53	6	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	54	6	11%					
Common Gull	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%					
European Herring Gull	0	0	0	0	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	20%					
Yellow-legged Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%					
Armenian Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	61	0	0%					
Sandwich Tern	0	0	0	0	121	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	121	1	1%					
Common Tern	4	0	0	0	62	1	0	0	0	31	0	0	0	0	0	97	1	1%					
Arctic Tern	0	0	0	0	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22	0	0%					
Little Tern	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0%					
Black Tern	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%					
<i>Corvids</i>																							
Eurasian Magpie	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0%					
Total	189	9	46	9	5	1	920	59	630	102	43	2	49	0	7	0	10	0	67	0	1966	182	9%

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FIGURE 1 Sample sites in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Sample sites for the 1,966 individuals sampled in Finland, Latvia, Lithuania, Sweden, Georgia, Austria, Germany, Switzerland, Italy, and Spain. The figure includes previously unpublished samples from June to October 2025.

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TABLE 2 Most recently collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of collected samples as well as number of samples positive for avian influenza virus. The table includes previously unpublished samples from June to October 2025.

Group/species	Node 1 Finland			Node 2 Latvia			Node 2 Lithuania			Node 2 Sweden			Node 4 Georgia			Node 6 Austria			Node 6 Germany			Node 6 Switzerland			Node 7 Italy			Node 9 Spain			Total		
	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI			
<i>Waterfowl</i>																																	
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	1	0
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0
Barnacle Goose	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	101	0	0
Mallard	72	9	0	28	5	1	0	0	0	697	141	0	200	42	0	4	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1004	198	1
Domestic Mallard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	62	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	62	15	0
Gadwall	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0
Northern Pintail	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
Northern Shoveler	4	0	0	7	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	15	4	0
Eurasian Wigeon	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0
Eurasian Teal	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	3	0	810	145	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	824	149	0
Garganey	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	2	0
Common Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	6	0
Red-crested Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Tufted Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0
Goldeneye	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Common Merganser	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
<i>Grebes</i>																																	
Great Crested Grebe	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Little Grebe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																																	
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	38	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	44	0	0
<i>Hérons</i>																																	
Black-crowned Night Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0
Western Cattle Egret	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0
Little Egret	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
<i>Storks, Ibises et al.</i>																																	
White Stork	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Glossy Ibis	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0
<i>Rails</i>																																	
Common Moorhen	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0
Eurasian Coot	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	59	0	0	62	0	0
<i>Waders</i>																																	
Black-winged Stilt	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0
Charadrius sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0
Little Ringed Plover	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30	0	0	0	0	0	38	0	0
Common Ringed Plover	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	38	0	0
Grey Plover	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
European Golden Plover	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Ruff	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0
Red Knot	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Purple Sandpiper	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Dunlin	111	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	110	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	225	0	0
Curlew Sandpiper	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	9	0	0
Temminck's Stint	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
Wood Sandpiper	27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	60	0	0
Green Sandpiper	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	8	0	0
Common Sandpiper	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0
Common Redshank	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0
Spotted Redshank	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Common Snipe	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0
<i>Larids</i>																																	
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	98	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	99	6	0
Common Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
European Herring Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	1	0
Yellow-legged Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Armenian Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	122	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	122	0	0
Sandwich Tern	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	239	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	239	1	0
Common Tern	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	109	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0</							

FIGURE 2 Weekly summary of collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In total, 18,502 samples (negative samples in blue; avian influenza virus-positive samples in orange) have been collected at seven nodes between August 2024 and October 2025, yielding 1,439 samples positive for avian influenza virus, including 25 samples positive for HPAI virus. The figures also include samples published in previous reports.

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2.2 GENOMICS SUMMARY

Since the last report was published on 7th of October (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17287099>), and as of 15th of October 2025, two new sequences have been generated from samples positive for H5 avian influenza virus. The two samples were collected from Mallards in Estonia (Node 1 Gulf of Finland) and Latvia (Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea) and were of the H5N2 and H5N1 subtypes, respectively. Genetic analysis of the haemagglutinin (HA) gene sequence of the H5N2 from Node 1 Gulf of Finland was found to belong to the H5 Eurasian avian non-goose Guangdong (EA-nonGsGd) low pathogenicity avian influenza (LPAI) clade, whilst the sequence from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea belonged to the H5 clade 2.3.4.4b of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) (Figure 3A).

The sequence from Estonia was found to be similar to other H5 LPAI sequences from the SENTINEL Wild bird project from Sweden (Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea) and France (Node 8 Camargue Region), as well as other Eurasian LPAI sequences (Figure 3B).

The sequence from Latvia, was determined to be the DI.2 genotype, according to the IZSve classification (<https://github.com/izsvenezie-virology/genin2>), and was found to be similar to another sequence from Latvia (a Whooper Swan), as well as sequences from Europe and surrounding countries, including the DI.2 sequence collected in Georgia (Node 4 Eastern Black Sea) in February 2025 (Figure 3C).

The Nextstrain builds are available on the SENTINEL Wild Birds Group (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/SentinelWildBirds>).

Apart from the H5 genome sequences, an additional H6N5 sequence was generated from a sample collected in Austria (Node 6 Lake Constance Region).

FIGURE 3 Phylogenetic analyses of the HA sequences generated by Node 1 Gulf of Finland and Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea. Image of the H5 HA sequences generated by the SENTINEL Wild Birds project, with the 2.3.4.4b and EA-nonGsGd clades highlighted. **B.** Zoom image of the HA tree focusing on the H5 low pathogenicity avian influenza (LPAI) EA-nonGsGd sequences from Node 1 Gulf of Finland, Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea and Node 8 Camargue Region. **C.** Zoom image of the HA tree focusing on the H5 highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) clade 2.3.4.4b sequences from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea and Node 4 Eastern Black Sea.

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3. CONCLUSION

With close to 2,000 individuals analysed from more than 50 species in 10 countries during the current period, the coverage of active surveillance of wild birds in and near Europe remains substantial. As expected during autumn, when a large immuno-naïve juvenile population is present, an increase in avian influenza virus (AIV) prevalence has been observed.

Positive samples were mainly found in dabbling ducks around the Baltic Sea, particularly in Mallards, as well as in Georgia, where Eurasian Teals dominated. In both regions, large numbers of ducks congregate at this time of year, making them key hotspots for active surveillance of avian influenza in wild birds. High bird-level prevalence was recorded in Eurasian Teal (19%), Mallard (13%), and Black-headed Gull (11%), all species with large sample sizes. Additionally, notably high prevalence was observed in some less frequently sampled species such as Common Pochard (4 of 9 individuals; 44%), Northern Shoveler (4 of 11; 36%), and Garganey (2 of 8; 25%).

Importantly, one sample from a hunted Mallard in Latvia tested positive for HPAI H5N1 virus. Genetic analysis showed that the virus belongs to clade 2.3.4.4b (genotype DI.2), similar to previous detections in Latvia and Georgia earlier this year. This highlights the need for continued vigilance and preparedness for potential outbreaks, particularly as autumn migration proceeds.

In addition to the HPAI case, virological analysis (by PCR) detected several other subtypes: one H13N6 in a European Herring Gull from Lithuania, one H3N2, one H6N5, one H12N2, and two H5Nx in Mallards from Latvia, as well as another H6N5 in a Mallard from Austria. These findings reflect the ongoing circulation and diversity of low pathogenic avian influenza (LPAI) viruses in the region.

Despite substantial sampling of waders (over 300 individuals), no AIV-positive samples were detected in this group. This may suggest that waders are not a priority target group for AIV surveillance under current resource constraints. However, it should be noted that most wader samples were collected in July–August, when overall prevalence is typically low. A similar observation applies to gulls and terns. With the exception of Black-headed Gulls, over 300 individuals were sampled with only three positives recorded.

The increase in positive detections around the Baltic Sea, especially in Latvia, combined with ongoing bird migration, underscores the importance of intensified monitoring at key stopover and wintering sites across Europe in the coming months.

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